

Role of Information Communication Technology in Enabling Sustainable Rural Extension: Case Analysis

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Abstract

In the 21st Century, Information plays a vital role in order to bring out a sustainable rural community welfare and development. To provide appropriate and adequate information to the rural community for enabling their livelihood development, the Village Knowledge Centre [VKC] has been implemented by the pioneer institution called “M.S.Swaminathan Research Foundation [MSSRF]” at village level with support of stakeholders in local functionaries basis. In this context, the present study is attempted to bring out the imperative of VKC for thriving influence on the rural community livelihood development in enabling sustainable rural extension. The Information Resources [IR] are measuring by its effect and impact on the VKC’s Users occupation and living condition for the study. Hence, the study has used the Case Study methodology to bring out the positive effect and impact of the IR on the living condition and occupation of the Users. In this direction scenario, initially Focus Group Discussions [FGD] conducted by the authors with Users, Village Knowledge Workers, Staff of Village Resource Centre [VRC], Boundary Partner, Village Panchayat representatives, Strategic Partners, and CBOs etc.

Based on the preliminary observations made in the FGD, the researchers have identified cases for further investigation so as to document the effect of the interventions made by the Village Knowledge Centre on the knowledge management by the Users and as a result in their living condition. This paper presents the Cases and discuss the effect and impact towards the rural community sustainable livelihood development for enabling rural extension. The Information is used for various purposes by the Villagers in their daily routine activity for enabling their

livelihood. It is focused on the influence of such information resources on the occupation of the Users. In this background the study presents the cases in order to measure the effectiveness of the Information Resource of the VKC for efficient rural extension.

Keywords: Rural Extension, Information Resources, Village Knowledge Centre, Welfare and Development, Knowledge Management

Learning New Farming Methods for Gaining

Case - 1. Mr. Subbiah is a farmer having five acres of land and he has been growing sapota, using vermi-compost and organic manure. He is a regular visitor to the VKC, Perumalkoilpatti which was instrumental in roping in more farmers like him in to organic farming. They have been sensitized on how to restore micronutrients and revitalized soil. He has been actively participated in training camps on organic plant protection, which was organized in the Perumalkoilpatti by VKC. This training paved a way for special study tour to various farms in order to enable the farmers to get on-farm experience and clarify doubts. Having understood the benefits of organic farming, he has stopped using chemical fertilizers and applies only organic manure and natural materials to give fresh lease of life to protect the soil health of his farm land. He could achieve the goal in improving physical properties of the soil. Most of the information on farming activities is passed on to the farmers through Mobile Messages, Tips given during the Soil Test Visit. He has regularly, participated in the Teleconference on organic farming. All these inputs have enabled him to adopt the innovative practices, they are presented below:

Waste Recycle as Manure and protect the soil moisture: He has dug L-shaped trenches around sapota tree and filled with organic wastes, cow dung and waste plants. Water has been supplied to plants through these trenches. Leaves withered from sapota trees too have been collected in these trenches to feed extra energy to plants. To preserve moisture content on the surface soil, topsoil is covered with coir pith and coconut husk that act as sponge to store water and supply it to roots continuously. Moisture on surface soil is also maintained for a long time.

He has adopted only natural pest control methods. A mixture of juices extracted from Neem Seed, Thumbai and Adathoda are the best pest-repellents to control pests attack. Availability of cattle is providing cow dung and used the same with bio-pesticide in his farm. In this case, participation in the training programmes, frequent visits to the VKC, following the text messages through mobile phone are considered as Interventions. The increased level of awareness on the new farming methods and adopting those practices are the effects of the interventions made by the VKC in the farming style of the farmer who is under study. Thus, the VKC has motivated farmers to shift towards organic farming practices. Therefore, Mr. Subbiah of Virudhalaipatti village has demonstrated the influence of the VKC on his farming system and management.

Enabled Women Entrepreneurs

Case - 2: Mrs. Chitharai Selvi, Nochiodaipatti, Dindigul she has studied up to 8th standard. Her husband is also completed only school level of education. They are getting meager wages for their hard work and they felt that as if, it is a terribly abject to them to live. They were expecting to get the right opportunity to come up in their life sustainable sources of livelihood. In this context, MSSRF through VKC conducted a Coconut Tree climbing Training Programme. She had an apprehension that as a woman, whether she can learn and use the technique of coconut tree climbing. She has asked the same doubt during the discussion with the researcher. According to her expressions, the VKC has explained and demonstrated how to climb with the help of coconut climbing machine in a comfortable manner without any technical nag.

She has participated in this programme with consent of her husband. During discussion, she has expressed that after training she is confident and fearless in her practice. During the course of the training, she has also learnt and acquired knowledge and skill about yoga and which contributed in maintaining her health fitness. After training, she has a coconut climbing machine which she is using to earn her livelihood. By that training, she is earning Rupees 300 per day which is really helping family and ensures livelihood security. Moreover, with improved earnings, she enabled to invest in the education of her children. In this job, she is able to serve 15 places which are nearby to her village. It is surely motivating and encouraging to many women as they are also coming forward to jointly start a Rural Women Coconut Climbers Association.

They are the pioneer and entrepreneurs in coconut climbers in Tami Nadu State and particularly in Dindigul District. These women coconut climbers association can serve various many villages and coconut farmers by offering coconut harvesting at a reasonable cost and also at the right time. During the discussions, she expressed that the traditional climbers demanding Rs.40 per tree and also with the condition that, after harvesting, the owner should also give the coconut climbers a minimum of 10 coconuts. On the contrary, our women coconut climbers' association team collects Rs. 10 per tree without any condition. These kinds of knowledge management and skill training inputs have really helped rural women to rise up for their socio-economic betterment and well-being in the contemporary environment. This case reveals that the VKC intervention has improved the women's Income generation skill and enabled the women talent to climb the coconut tree. The VKC also has increased the confident level and knowledge of women and also combine the women climbers as together for a common goal.

Boosting Employability

Case - 3: P. Maheswari [32], completed Higher Secondary level of schooling and she is working as Computer Operator. She is residing at Pilliyarnatham. Her husband is working in a private cotton mill for a meagre wage. Hence, they need to earn sufficient income to run their family. With the presences of two school going children in her family, compulsorily she required to earn more income to run the family. At that this critical background, she has attended SHG federation monthly meeting as a SHG member. During that meeting, The Village Knowledge Worker of Pillaiyarnatham- VKC has also participated and explained about the functions of VKC and also emphasized the free computer literacy course that increase opportunity to get an employment . Attracted by this impressive speech by VKC Staff and the VKC is located in a place which is accessible to her. Besides, the factors such as location, timings, trainer of the VKC are supportive to her and attract her for the training programme. Hence, she has discussed with husband and joined the computer course. She has found that the course was very relevant to her and also taught in local language. These advantages have helped her to complete the course. After completion of the training programme in M.S. Office, she got a job in the Spinning Mill as Computer Operator with a salary of Rupees 15,000 per month. It has energized y that more financial resources and increased confident level to run the family. This case reveals that the Intervention of VKC has enabled the ICT literacy to rural and increased the opportunity to earn financial resources for their livelihood development.

Case - 4: K. Maharajan [28], has studied only Higher Secondary education. He is residing at Koolapatti with his parents and his wife. His father is electrician and mother is an agriculture coolie. He is running a Photo Studio at Sempatti. He has known about the VKC through his friends and also about the Computer course organized in the VKC. He has joined the computer course and completed the same. After three months, he became first computer literate in his family. After completing the programme he got new opportunity to work at Sempatti in a private photo studio

with guidance has given by Village Knowledge Work. He worked for Rupees 2500 as honorarium to one year at private photo studio during the time he got major doubts in Photoshop at the moment; he frequently visited VKC and clarified all the doubts with support of village knowledge worker. During the working time at photo studio, he gained the full knowledge to operate a photo studio especially in preparation of Photo Album, Still Photographs and videos and also taking photos and video at orders such as marriage and temple festival. He has decided and discussed with village knowledge worker and parents to start a photo studio. They have motivated him to start a photo studio business. After quitting the job and he invested Rupees. 1, 00,000 to start a new own photo studio at sempatti. The financial support has made available by his parents through bank loan. His business has got a good opportunity from its inception, so that, he has cleared all the loans which he has taken from bank. Besides, a new house constructed at village with his increased earnings of Rupees. 30,000pm. He proudly said that he has become socially, economically strong only through the Digital Literacy given by VKC. This case reveals that the VKC intervention has enabled him to become a first computer literate and an entrepreneur.

Access to Information Resource and its Impact

Case - 5: Preethi is 20 years old and residing at Athoor, Dindigul district. She belongs to a poor family. She was brought up by mother with meager earnings after death of her father when she was 11 years old, it was diagnosed that she has Heart Problem, in one of the Medical Camps organized by the VKC. This has brought life time threat to her and which has posed serious problems to the family members in terms of financial burden in providing health care immediately. In this crucial condition, with intervention of MSSRF, the VKC - Pillaiyarnatham has arranged a teleconference facility with Narayana Kiruthalaya Hospital, Bangalore. On that teleconference and discussions on the issue, the Doctors agreed to do surgery at the reduced cost Rupees One lakh. But, it was still not feasible for her family to mobilise required funds to provide treatment. At the time MSSRF has decided to shoulder the responsibility of making arrangement of financial assistance required for surgery. The Chairman of the MSSRF, Dr. M.S. Swaminathan was the Member of Parliament [M.P] and he has sanctioned required amount from this Constituency Development fund so as to get Rupees One lakh meet the expenses of medical treatment and transportation. She has gone to heart surgery immediately, and there has done surgery successfully and returned back to her home. After that surgery she and her family came down to normal life. At present she is doing under graduate course in one private college of Dindigul. The highlight of the case is that the available facility in the VKC for Teleconference with any expert working anywhere in India or Abroad. The KVC has provided vital information on the experts in the field of Heart health care that enabled the rural poor girl to get access to the Doctor and also funds by way of Converging development scheme of the Constituency Development fund. The key factor is the source of information resource and its accessibility.

The noteworthy inference from the case is that VKC is acting a Rural Extension Service centre to provide required information and guidance to the rural poor. The VKC is not only provides information, but also help the less educated or illiterate to get the services from the government department or agencies. This is one more case for how the VKC is influencing on the living standards of the rural people by providing information resources.

Conclusion

The presented cases are demonstrated how the VKC supports to enable the rural extension by its user friendly services in providing information resources to the rural people for converting information into knowledge in order to enable their sustainable development and welfare and also

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scaling up their livelihood standards towards create a win-win platform more vibrantly. The effect and welfare consequences are summarised below:

Case	Sector	Inputs	Outcome - Result	Effect	Impact
1	Organic farming	Training Programme	Increased awareness on organic farming methods	Development of positive attitude among the participants on the organic farming	Inclination to adoption of methods learned on Organic farming
		Regular visit to VKC	Knowledge on farming increased Improved access to information on Organic farming	Increased confidence to apply the knowledge acquired on farming methods	Interest to apply in farming methods and shift towards organic farming
2	Skill Development	Technical Training on Knowledge and Guidance to Climb the Coconut Tree by women	Improved knowledge and Skill for Climbing of Coconut Tree	Implement the learnt skills for the livelihood and earnings	Increased the earning opportunity
3	ICT – Literacy	Training on increased employment opportunity to work as a Computer Operator	Improved the knowledge on computer handling techniques	Improved the technical knowledge	Opportunity to earn by learning new skills and ICT application
4	Entrepreneurship	Training and Consulting to start a Photo Studio	Increased skill on aspects of Photo Studio Operations	Developed positive attitude to start a business	Enabled to regularly earn from the Photo Studio Operations
5	Health care	Information Resource through Teleconference by consultancy service to cure the Heart Problem	Increased knowledge has enabled the accessibility of the expert	Increased financial opportunity is made positive confident level	Health Care Service accessed and resulted in improvement of the health

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